

(Table 1 Contd.)

7.	"	4-OCH ₃	112	60
8.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	108	45
9.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	140	50
10.	"	3-NO ₂	98	65
11.	"	4-NO ₂	100	70
12.	R=3-NO ₂	H	140	50
13.	"	2-OH ₃	153	60
14.	"	3-CH ₃	137	65
15.	"	4-CH ₃	120	65
16.	"	2-OCH ₃	176	50
17.	"	3-OCH ₃	182	45
18.	"	4-OCH ₃	143	55
19.	R=3-NO ₂	2-OC ₂ H ₅	140	50
20.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	123	45
21.	"	3-NO ₂	110	60
22.	"	4-NO ₂	96	65
23.	R=2-NO ₂	H	169	60
24.	"	2-OH ₃	152	55
25.	"	3-OH ₃	147	60
26.	"	4-OH ₃	132	65
27.	"	2-OCH ₃	127	50
28.	"	3-OCH ₃	176-178	50
29.	"	4-OCH ₃	150	45
30.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	143	50
31.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	160	55
32.	"	3-NO ₂	120	65
33.	"	4-NO ₂	107-109	65

All compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

Acknowledgement

Authors are highly thankful to Dr. Wahid U. Malik, Vice-Chancellor, Kashmir University, Srinagar for his interest and guidance. They are also thankful to U. G. C. and C. S. I. R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

- O. T. SAVULESCU, V. BARBU and V. TUDOESCU, *Phytopathol Z.*, 1967, **59**, 129.
- E. PROFFT, H. TRUBNER and W. WREUFFEN, *Arch. Exp. Veterinaermed.*, 1967, **21**, 225.
- Can. Patent No. 820 919 (1969), *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **71**, 124012.
- S. C. SHARMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Japan)*, 1967, **40**, 2422.
- B. DASH and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 663.
- M. Y. MHASALKAR, M. H. SHAH, K. G. ANANTHARYAN and C. V. PELIVALA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 260.
- H. G. GARG and R. A. SHARMA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, **59**, 348.

Studies on Bromophenols. Part I—Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-2-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-Bromo-5'-Methylphenyl)-3-Aryl-5 H/Methyl/Carboxymethyl-4-Thiazolidinones

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Manuscript received 20 November 1980, accepted 9 June 1981

BROMOPHENOLS possess antibacterial¹, antifungal², antiseptic³, germicidal⁴ and other biological activities. 4-Thiazolidinones are also associated with various kinds of biological activities

like hypnotic⁵, anaesthetic⁶, antifungal⁷ etc. With a view to get more active drugs we have prepared 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) containing bromophenol residue by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases which were obtained by condensing 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzophenone⁸ with different aromatic amines. The constitution was supported by ir spectra⁹⁻¹¹. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

(I)

R = Aryl
R₁ = H, CH₃, OH, COOH

IR spectra: The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) were taken on KBr pellets and characterised. The >C=O group frequency was obtained at 1640 nm, >N-CO at 1590 nm and phenolic OH at 3410 nm.

Experimental

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil: Aniline (0.1 mole) was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzophenone (0.1 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 75%, m.p. 62°. (Found: C, 65.35; H, 4.50; N, 3.75%. C₂₀H₁₆NOBr requires, C, 65.57; H, 4.37; N, 3.83%). Other anils were prepared similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 1).

Preparation of 2-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone: Thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 61%, m.p. 78°. (Found: C, 60.25; H, 4.00; N, 3.25. C₂₂H₁₈NO₂SBr requires C, 60.00; H, 4.09; N, 3.18%). Other anils were treated with thioglycolic acid similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 2).

Preparation of 2-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone: Thiolactic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 67%, m.p. 68°. (Found: C, 60.75; H, 4.50; N, 3.00. C₂₃H₂₀NO₂SBr requires C, 60.53; H, 4.41; N, 3.08%). Other anils were treated with thiolactic acid similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 2).

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF ANILS

Sl. No.	R	Molecular Formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition in mm	
					<i>S. aureus</i> (24 hrs)	<i>B. megatarum</i> (24 hrs)
1.	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ NOBr	62	75	12	15
2.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Br	245	51	14	12
3.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Br	125	51	11	12
4.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ NOBrCl	279	65	11	10
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NOBr	65	80	9	15
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NOBr	75	62	11	10
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NOBr	110	59	16	12
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NO ₂ Br	246	77	12	14
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ NO ₂ Br	200	68	9	16
10.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ NO ₂ Br	90	90	10	11
11.	α -Naphthyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ NOBr	255	68	14	10

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES OF TYPE I

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular Formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition in mm		
						<i>S. aureus</i> (24 hrs)	<i>B. megatarium</i> (24 hrs)	<i>E. Coli</i> (24 hrs)
1.	Phenyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ NO ₂ SBr	78	61	19	16	9
2.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ SBr	75	76	14	15	10
3.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ SBr	115	72	18	16	8
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ NO ₂ SBrCl	69-71	68	13	12	11
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	74	52	11	18	10
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	87-89	61	12	13	9
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	77	58	18	17	12
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	70	68	16	16	6
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	83	74	16	17	8
10.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	72	80	16	14	7
11.	α -Naphthyl	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	140	60	16	13	10
12.	Phenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ NO ₂ SBr	68	67	13	16	6
13.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ SBr	72	71	15	15	8
14.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ SBr	128	76	13	16	9
15.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ NO ₂ SBrCl	66	52	10	10	5
16.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	59	58	12	17	7
17.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	82	66	7	10	9
18.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	75	70	15	13	9
19.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	77	72	13	14	9
20.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	73	55	11	18	7
21.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ NO ₂ SBr	69	65	15	12	7
22.	α -Naphthyl	CH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	280	80	15	10	6
23.	Phenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ NO ₄ SBr	75	32	—	17	—
24.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	"	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ SBr	78	38	—	13	—
25.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	"	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ SBr	64	40	—	15	—
26.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	"	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ NO ₂ SBrCl	78	49	—	13	—
27.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	"	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	71	34	—	22	—
28.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	"	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	70	51	—	11	—
29.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	"	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	63	42	—	15	—
30.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	"	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	78	48	—	16	—
31.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	"	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	80	52	—	18	—
32.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	"	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ NO ₂ SBr	74	38	—	13	—
33.	α -Naphthyl	"	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ NO ₂ SBr	85	34	—	17	—

Nitrogen analysis for all the compounds in consistent with their formulae.

Preparation of 2-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : α -Phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mole) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mole) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 30 min (Reddelien method¹²). The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 32%, m.p. 72°. (Found : C, 57.50; H, 4.20; N, 2.75. C₂₄H₂₀NO₄SBr requires C, 57.83; H, 4.02; N, 2.81%). Other anils were treated with thiomalic acid similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 2).

Antimicrobial screening : The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate method¹³ using a species of gram positive bacteria, i.e., *S. aureus*, *B. megaterium* and a species of gram negative bacteria, i.e., *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in ethanol solution at a concentration 10 mg/ml. The zones of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) were recorded.

The anils are active against gram positive bacteria only while 4-thiazolidinones containing 5-H/methyl are active against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria. Moreover, they possess

good activity when R=phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl or *p*-anisyl. In case of 4-thiazolidinones, the compounds containing 5-carboxymethyl are active against *B. megaterium* only.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for research facilities and a research scholarship to one of them (R. R. S.).

References

1. I. M. BORTOVOI, G. L. RYZHOVA, *Izv. Tomsk. Politakh. Inst.*, 1959, 102 71; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 12042a.
2. G. VIEL, M. CHANCOGNE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Biol.*, 1958, 40, 1617; *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 5573h.
3. SCHÜBLCE UND MAYR, G.m.b.H. *Appl.* 11 Sept., 1974, 74130, 761; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, 83, 48226u.
4. A. S. CRAFTS, *Weeds*, 1960, 8, 19; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 55, 17998i.
5. J. DORAN and H. A. SHONLE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 193.
6. H. D. TROUTMAN and M. M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 10, 3436.
7. J. KINUGAWA and K. NEGASE, Japanese Patent, 8542; *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 63, 5653h.
8. NG. PH. BUU-BIO and DERRIEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 20.
9. F. C. BROWN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 463.
10. D. H. WILLIAMS and I. FLAMMING, "Spectroscopy Methods in Organic Chemistry," McGraw Hill Publishing Company, 1966, p. 68.
11. R. ROYER, A. EHEUTIN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1956, 302, 1279; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 50, 11279d.
12. G. REDDELIEN, *Ber.*, 1919, 2712, 2718; 1920, 345.
13. F. CAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology," Academic Press Inc., New York, 1963, p. 126.

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Halogeno-chalcones

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Manuscript received 10 October 1979, accepted 5 November 1980

CHALCONES have bactericidal¹⁻³, fungicidal⁴, germicidal⁵⁻⁸ activity. Considering these facts various hydroxy halogeno-chalcones have been prepared expecting antimicrobial activity.

α -Naphthaldehyde or 2-methoxy- α -naphthaldehyde, on keeping with hydroxy acetophenones in presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution for 16-24 hrs and subsequent acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid, yielded the products (Table 1). The products gave positive Wilson test⁹ (yellow colouration) vivid colours on wetting with concentrated sulphuric acid and violet red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The structures were confirmed by elemental analysis and infrared spectra.

3', 5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy and 3', 5'-diiodo-4'-hydroxy acetophenones were prepared from 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone and 4'-hydroxy acetophenones respectively by iodination with iodine and iodic acid. 3', 5'-Diiodo-2'-hydroxy and 3', 5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy-5',6-benzochalcones were also prepared from 2'-hydroxy and 2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy-5',6-benzochalcones respectively by iodination with iodine and iodic acid.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc.

Infrared spectra of these compounds (Table 2) in Nujol mulls showed the conjugated carbon carbon double bond band at 1600-1550 cm⁻¹ and carbonyl stretching frequency at 1655-1610 cm⁻¹. These assignments are in agreement with those observed by Mahanty *et al*¹⁰ for chalcones.

Experimental

Preparation of 5', 6-benzochalcones: Chalcones were prepared by adding 10% potassium hydroxide (10-20 ml) to an equimolar aldehyde and ketone solution in ethyl alcohol and keeping the reaction mixture at 60° for 16 hrs. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ice cold water. On acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid it gave a yellow product. All the chalcones gave yellow colouration in Wilson test⁹ and pink to dark red colouration with conc. sulfuric acid.

3',5'-Diiodo-2'-hydroxy acetophenone: 2'-Hydroxy acetophenone (0.1639 g) and iodine (2.03 g) were dissolved in ethyl alcohol (50 ml) and heated to about 60°. Iodic acid (0.29 g) in water (2 ml) added with stirring over 0.5 hr. The reaction mixture was then treated with saturated sodium bisulphite solution to decompose the excess of iodine. The separated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m. p. 127°. Mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen of 3',5'-diiodo-2'-hydroxy acetophenone¹¹ was undepressed, yield 0.35 g (Found: I, 65.93; C₈H₆O₂I₂ requires I, 65.46%).

3',5'-Diiodo-4'-hydroxy acetophenone: 4'-Hydroxy acetophenone (0.163 g) and iodine (2.023 g) in ethanol (70 ml) were heated to 60° and iodic acid (0.29 g) in water (2 ml) was added to it with stirring over 0.5 hr. On working up as before the product separated, which was crystallised from ethyl alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 158°, yield 0.32 g (Found: I, 65.69; C₈H₆O₂I₂ requires I, 65.46%).

Iodination of 2'-hydroxy and 2'-hydroxy-2-methoxy-5', 6-benzochalcones: Benzochalcones (0.01 M) and iodine in excess (0.08 M) were dissolved in ethyl alcohol 50 ml and heated to about 60° and iodic acid (0.3 g) in water added with stirring over 1 hr. The product was obtained on working up as before and crystallised from ethyl alcohol in colourless needles. M. P. and other data are given in Tables 1 and 2.